

A REVIEW OF SARPAGANDHA IN AYURVEDIC CLASSICS AND NIGHANTUS

Akshay Varshney^{*1}, Ramakant Marde², Priyanka Soni³, Gitika⁴

¹*3rd Year P.G. Scholar, Department of Dravyaguna Vigyana, Patanjali Bhartiye Ayurvedic Evam Anusandhan Sansthan, Haridwar, Uttarakhand, India.

²Professor, H.O.D. Department of Dravyaguna Vigyana, Patanjali Bhartiye Ayurvedic Evam Anusandhan Sansthan, Haridwar, Uttarakhand, India.

³Professor, Department of Dravyaguna Vigyana, Patanjali Bhartiye Ayurvedic Evam Anusandhan Sansthan, Haridwar, Uttarakhand, India.

⁴Assistant Professor, Department of Dravyaguna Vigyana, Baba Hira Das Ji Ayurvedic Medical College, V.P.O. Badal, Sri Muksar Sahib.

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*Corresponding Author

Akshay Varshney

3rd Year P.G. Scholar, Department of Dravyaguna Vigyana, Patanjali Bhartiye Ayurvedic Evam Anusandhan Sansthan, Haridwar, Uttarakhand, India.

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ABSTRACT

Sarpagandha Rauwolfia serpentina (L.) Benth. ex Kurz is a member of the family *Apocynaceae*. It is a plant that commonly grows in mountains and hilly regions. The roots look like a *Sarpa* (Snake) with a peculiar smell. The flowers are red in colour. The fruit resembles the eye of a snake, and the plant had exudation. *Sarpagandha* is said to have *Katu-Tikta-Kasaya* in *Rasa* and *Ruksha* in *Guna*, *Ushna* in *Veerya*, *Katu* in *Vipaka*, and is said to have *Kaphavatahara* and *Nidrajanana* property. It is used in the management of *Shoola*, *Jwara*, *Unmada*, and *Raktavata*. Modern pharmacological studies explain its role as a cardio-depressant, antihelminthic, carminative, digestive, febrifuge, etc. *Sarpagandha* was reviewed in various texts like the *Veda*, *Samhita*, *Nighantus*, and *Kosha Grantha*. *Sarpagandha* was found to be the main ingredient of *Sarpagandhadi Vati*, *Sarpagandhadi Churna*, and *Sarpagandha yoga*. Various *Paryaya*, *Guna*, *Karma*, and different opinions of *Acharyas* in various *Nighantu* were reviewed.

KEYWORDS: *Sarpagandha, Raktavata, Nighantu, Samhita, Unmada.*

INTRODUCTION

An extensive review of *Sarpagandha* was done in many *Ayurvedic Samhitas*, including those in the *Charak Samhita, Sushruta Samhita, Ashtanghrdaya, Ashtangasangraha, Bhela, Harita, Kashyap*, and other *Samhitas* like *Gadanigraha, Kalyanakarakam, Siddhasara Samhita* etc. *Sarpagandha* here was found to be a very effective herb being a part of many formulations in treatment of diseases like *Vrana, Krimi, Sarpa, Luta, Vrischika, Mooshika* and *Garavisha* etc. A detailed review of *Sarpagandha* was done in many *Nighantus* from the ancient times to the most recent. It came across that too many synonyms being common in every *Nighantu* like *Nakuli, Surasa, Nagsugandha, Gandhanakuli, Nakuleshta, Bhujangakshi, Sarpangi, Vishanashini, Sarpagandha, Sugandha, Raktapatrika*, has been mentioned in multiple *Nighantus*. A detailed review of *Sarpagandha* was also done in *Rasa Granthas* like *Rastarangini* and *Rasaratnasamuccaya* and various *Kosha* like *Shiva Kosha, Vachaspatyam* and *Amar Kosha*.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

1. *Sarpagandha* in *Samhita* Period

1.1. *Susruta Samhita*^[1,2]

The *Susruta Samhita* is an *Ayurvedic* treatise that specifically deals with *Shalya Chikitsa*. *Susruta Samhita* was originally written by *Acharya Susruta* and amended by *Nagarjuna*. It had descriptions of a wide range of illnesses, covering diagnosis, symptoms, and modes of treatment, and focuses on surgical management. This book covers preoperative, operative, and postoperative measures and provides surgical methods in a methodical manner. *Sarpagandha* is mentioned as ingredient of *Eksar Yoga in Sarpavisha, Arunaadi-Panch-Sarpa-Dansta-Chikitsa, Sarvagrahadosha*.

1.2 *Astanghrdaya*^[3] (7th Century A.D.)

The *Astangahrdaya* is a well-known, extremely significant classical text with excellent educational value. The large number of commentaries written by Indian scholars attests to its popularity. It has cemented its position as one of the main *Ayurvedic* treatises in the *Brihatrayi*. It is composed of the views of *Charak, Susruta, and Astangasangraha*. It gives an interface about *Raktanirharan, Vasti prayog, Shilajeet prayog* and *Agrya dravyas*. *Sarpagandha* is mentioned as ingredient of *Grahabhootnashak-Hinguadi Yoga*.

1.3 *Vaidyaprasarakam*^[4] (9th century A.D.)

This treatise includes the description of various *Ayurvedic* formulations for the treatment of various disorders. *Sarpagandha* is mentioned as ingredient of *Jatyaadikam Tailam*, *Bhootpratishede Vasti*, *Dhadhi-taila-ghritair-alodhya-deya*.

1.4 *Yogratnasammuchaya*^[5] (10th century A.D.)

Written by *Vaidyasiromani Acharya Candrata*, this ancient *ayurvedic* book dates back 1100 years. *Acharya Candrata* was the son of *Vaidya Tisatacharya*. More than 50 ancient Indian script writers were consulted in the writing of this old *Ayurveda Candra*.

Sarpagandha is mentioned as ingredient of *Paisachika Ghrita*, *Jatyaadi Taila*.

1.5 *Cakradatta*^[6] (11th century A.D.)

The well-known treatise *Cakradatta* was written by *Cakrapanidatta*. Another name for it is the *Chikitsa sangraha* of *Cakrapanidatta*. This work established a historical benchmark for the evolution of medical theories and procedures in antiquity. This treatise contains numerous original pharmaceutical formulas. *Sarpagandha* is mentioned as ingredient of *Palankashadhya Tailam*.

1.6 *Gadanigraha*^[7] (12th century A.D.)

Gadanigraha is a popular treatise written by *Vaidya Sodhala*. It has a lot of unique formulations. *Sarpagandha* is mentioned as ingredient of *Chaturthak Mahapaisachik Ghritam*, *Sannipatjware Jatyaaditailam*, *Bhootounmada Aparajito Agad*.

1.7 *Vaidyamanorama*^[8] (13th century A.D.)

This book, written by *Shri Kalidas*, contains descriptions and treatments of various diseases. It is divided into 20 *Patala* (chapters), and a lot of medicinal formulations are described. *Sarpagandha* is mentioned as a drug used in *Ajeerna* after *Vaman Karma* in case of emaciation. It is mentioned as an ingredient of *Kaksha-vidhradhi-visarpahara taila*, *Vartigrahaadi- Lepa*.

1.8 *Basavarajeeyam*^[9] (15th-16th century A.D.)

Basavarajeeyam is a famous treatise in *Ayurveda* followed in various parts of the country, apart from its popularity in Andhra Pradesh. *Pandit Sri Govardhan Sharma Changani* is credited with translating this work into *Sanskrit*. It contains herbs mentioned in *Sanskrit* verses and also contains *Rasa Yogas*.

Sarpagandha is mentioned under herbs as *Nakuli*.

2 Classification of *Sarpagandha* in different Classics

Classical text	Gana/ Varga/ Others	Adhyaya shloka no.
<i>Susruta Samhita</i>	<i>Eksar Yoga in Sarpavisha.</i> <i>Arunaadi-Panch-Sarpa-Dansta-Chikitsa.</i> <i>Sarvagrahadosa</i>	<i>Su. Ka. 5/84</i> <i>Su.Ka.7/29</i> <i>Su. Ut. 60/48</i>
<i>Astangahrdaya</i>	<i>Grahahootnashak-Hinguadi Yoga</i>	<i>Ah. Ut.5/3</i>
<i>Vaidyaprasarakam</i>	<i>Jatyaadikam Tailam.</i> <i>Bhootpratishede Vasti.</i> <i>Dhadhi-taila-ghritair-alodhya-deya.</i>	<i>Vai. Pr. 4</i> <i>Vai. Pr. 8</i> <i>Vai. Pr. 10</i>
<i>Yogratnasammuchaya</i>	<i>Paisachika Ghrita.</i> <i>Jatyaadi Taila.</i>	<i>Pg. 51</i> <i>Pg. 56</i>
<i>Cakradatta</i>	<i>Palankashadhya Tailam</i>	<i>Cak. 32/31-33</i> <i>Pg. 132</i>
<i>Gadanigraha</i>	<i>Chaturthak Mahapaisachik Ghritam.</i> <i>Sannipatjware Jatyaaditailam.</i> <i>Bhootounmada Aparajito Agad</i>	<i>Gd 1/396-99</i> <i>Pg. 62</i> <i>Gd 2/271-75 Pg</i> <i>109-110</i> <i>Gd 1/54-60 Pg</i> <i>407-408</i>
<i>Vaidyamanorama</i>	<i>Kaksha-vidhradhi-visarpahara taila.</i> <i>Vartigrahaadi- Lepa.</i>	<i>Vai.Mano.11/13</i> <i>Pg. 78</i> <i>Vai.Mano.16/99</i> <i>Pg. 171</i>
<i>Basavarajeeyam</i>	<i>Mentioned as Nakuli</i>	<i>Page 53</i>

3 Description of *Sarpagandha* in different *Nighantus*

3.1 *Paryayaratnamala*^[10] (9th century A.D.)

Madhava's Paryayaratnamala is one of the most well-known works of Indian materia medica. It is known by the popular name *Ratnamala*. This work functions as a thorough medical lexicon, or *Nighnatu*, and includes many synonyms. Synonyms of *Sarpagandha* are given as *Rishyagandha*, *Sarpagandha*, and *Rishijangalika*.

3.2 *Madanadi Nighantu*^[11] (10th century A.D.)

Written in the 10th century A.D. by *Candranandan*, also known as *Candra-nighantu*. The reason *Madanadi Nighantu* got its name is that it deals with medications that are listed in *Astangahrdaya's Madanadigana*. There is also a portion of random *dravya* in it. In *Prakareenya Ausadha Dravya of Uttar Bhaga*, *Sarpagandha* has been described as the first variety, as *Nakuli* with synonyms like *Nakuli*, *Sarpagandha*, *Sugandha*, *Atigandhika*,

Sarpasugandha, *Ciritaptraka*. It is mentioned as *Tikta* in *Rasa*, *Kashaya in Anurasa*, *Bhedana*, *Luta-Vrana-Nivarak*, and is used in all types of *Visha* (poisons). The Second variety *Gandhanakuli* with synonyms like *Mahasugandha*, *Subaha*, *Gandhanakuli*, *Sarpakshi*, *Nakuleshta*, *Chatraki*, *Vishamardini*, *Sugandha*, *Nagmadani*, *Shankha*, *Shankhamalini*, *Tiriti*, *Shankhacusuma*, *Medhya*, and *Vanavilsaini*, is mentioned, along with properties like *Rasayan* properties, *Medhya* and *Kushtha- Apasmara-Nashak*. It is *Tikta in Rasa*, *Tridosha-hara*, *Sheeta in Virya*.

3.3 *Dhanvantari Nighantu*^[12] (11th century A.D.)

This *Nighantu* is very popular among scholars and has enormous significance in the field of *dravyaguna*. Its precise duration is still unknown. While some groups incorrectly regard it to be the oldest *Nighantu* because of its relationship with the holy name “*Dhanvantari*,” this is not right. The author of this book is credited in multiple manuscripts as *Mahendra Bhogika*, who is the son of *Krishna Bhogika*. *Sarpagandha* has been described under the fourth chapter in *Karveeradi varga*, as *Nakuli* with synonyms like *Sarpagandha*, *Sugandha*, *Bhogigandhika*, *Sarpasugandha*, *Ciritaptraka*. Its properties mentioned as *Ushna in virya*, *Katu-Tikta in Rasa*, used in *Krimi Roga* and *Mooshika Visha*.

3.4 *Nighantu Sesa*^[13] (12th century A.D.)

The *Nighantu*, penned by *Hemacandracharya Suri*, is extremely valuable. The author is also known as *Jainacharya Hemchandra*. This *Nighantu* describes many herbs and includes their synonyms and medicinal qualities. Subject matter has been divided into six *Kandas*. In *Gulma kanda*, four synonyms of *Sarpagandha* are mentioned as *Nakulya*, *Sarpagandha*, *Sugandha*, *Ciritaptraka*.

3.5 *Sodhala Nighantu*^[14] (12th century A.D.)

Sodhala-nighantu or *Nighantu of Sodhala* or *Nighantusara sangraha* or *Nighantusarvasva* is based on the Indian *Materia Medica*. It is authored by *Acharya Sodhala*. This *Nighantu* is divided into two parts. The first part is available by the name of *Namasangraha*, and the second part by the name of *Gunasangraha*. *Sarpagandha* is described in *Guduchyadi Varga*, as *Gandhanakuli* with synonyms like *Nakulya*, *Gandhamoola*, *Sugandha*, *Subaha*, *Surbhi*, *Sarpagandha*, *Gandhakhya*, *Gandhacharini* are described.^[69] In *Karveeradi Varga*, it is described as *Nakuli* with synonyms like *Nakulya*, *Sarpagandha*, *Sugandha*, *Chirnapatrika*, *Ishwari*, *Surasa*, *Rasna*, *Bhujangadamnishyte* are described. But *Guna karma* is not mentioned in this *Nighantu*.

3.6 *Abhidhanaratnamala*^[15] (12th – 13th century A.D.)

It is also known as *Sadrasa Nighantu*, is a synonymous style of *Nighantu*. The reason this *Nighantu* is called *Sadrasa* is that its contents are arranged into six chapters based on personal preference. In *Katu Dravya Skanda Sarpagandha* is mentioned as *Sarpakshi* with synonyms like *Sarpakshi*, *Nakuli*, *Kshiri*, *Sarpagandha*, *Sugandhika*, are described.

3.7 *Hridayadipaka Nighantu*^[16] (13th century A.D.)

Pandit Bopadeva is the author of the *Hridayadipaka-nighantu*, a significant and authenticated book divided into eight sections. In this *Nighantu*, *Sarpagandha* is mentioned under *Chatushpada varga as Nakuli* with synonyms like *Nakuli*, *Sarpagandha*, *Vishaghni*, *Sarpalochana* are described, another variety is mentioned as *Gandhanakuli*, with synonyms like *Sarpasugandha*, *Sugandha*, and *Gandhanakuli*, are described.

3.8 *Madanapala Nighantu*^[17] (1374 century A.D.)

Madana-nighantu and *Madanavinoda* are other names for *Madanapala Nighantu*. The author of this treatise is *Nripa Madanapala*. In *Abhayadi Varga*, *Sarpagandha* is described as *Nakuli* with synonyms like *Sarpagandha*, *Dhawalvarua*, *Chota-chand*, *Nakuli*, *Nakulkanda*, *Dhanvarua*, *Gandharasna*, *Harkai-chandra* are described. Its properties are *Katu-Tikta-Kashay* in *Rasa*, *Ushna* in *Virya*, used in *Luta*, *Vrischik*, *Aakhu*, *Sarpa Visha*, *Krimi Roga*, *Vrana Nashak*.

3.9 *Raja Nighantu*^[18] (14th century A.D.)

Raja Nighantu was originally called *Abhidhanacudamani*. *Nighanturaja* and *Dravyabhidhanagana Sangraha* are some other names for it. The author is *Narhari Pandita*. In *Moolakadi varga*, *Sarpagandha* is mentioned as *Nakuli* with synonyms like *Nakuli*, *Sarpagandha*, *Sugandha*, *Raktapatrika*, *Ishwari*, *Nagagandha*, *Ahibhuka*, *Swarasa*, *Sarpadini*, *Vyaalgandha*, are described, with second variety, as *Mahasugandha* with synonyms like *Mahasugandha*, *Subaha*, *Gandhanakuli*, *Sarpakshi*, *Fadihantri*, *Nakuladhya*, *Ahibhuka*, *Ahimardini*, *Vishamardini*, *Mahahigandha*, *Ahilata* are described, Its properties are *Katu-Tikta* in *Rasa*, *Ushna* in *Virya*, *Tridosha-shamak* and used in different types of *Visha* and the second variety is better than the first variety.

3.10 *Kaiyadeva Nighantu*^[19] (1425 A.D.)

The original name of this treatise, authored by *Kaiyadeva*, is *Pathyapathya vibhodka*.

In *Aushadhi Varga Sarpagandha* is described as *Nakuli* with synonyms like *Nakuleshta*, *Mahavirya*, *Sarpasugandhika*, *Vishaghni*, *Subaha*, *Sarpagandha*, *Ciritaptraka*, *Sugandha*, *Nakuli*, *Sarpalochana*, *Gandhanakuli*, *Sarpakankalika*, *Sunanda*, *Vishadranshtika*, *Mahasudha*, *Chatraki*, *Kamacharini* are mentioned. Its properties are *Katu-Kashaya-Tikta* in *Rasa*, used in *Vrana*, *Krimi Roga*, *Sarpa*, *Luta*, *Vrischika*, *Mushka Visha*, *Gara Visha*.

3.11 *Bhavaprakasa Nighantu*^[20] (16th century A.D.)

This important *Ayurvedic* book is regarded as one of *Bhavamisra's* canonical works. This *Nighantu* acts as a link between the present and the medieval era. In this *Nighantu*, *Sarpagandha* has been described in *Haritakyadi-varga*, with synonyms like *Nakuli*, *Surasa*, *Nagsugandha*, *Gandhanakuli*, *Nakuleshta*, *Bhujakankshi*, *Sarpangi*, *Vishanashini*, are described. Its properties are *Kashaya-Tikta-Katu* in *Rasa*, *Ushna* in *Virya*, used in *Sarpa*, *Luta*, *Vrischik*, *Aakhu Visha*, with *Jwara*, *Krimi Roga*, *Vrana Shamaka*.

3.12 *Paryayamuktavali*^[21] (1887 A.D.)

This book was a creation of *Haricaranasena Utkal*. Initially named *Muktavali* is based on *Amarkosh* and *Paryayaratnamala*, consists of 23 Chapters. In *Tambulyaadilata varga*, *Sarpagandha* is mentioned with synonyms like *Rishyagandha*, *Sarpagandha*, *Rishijangalika* are mentioned.

3.13 *Shaligrama Nighantu*^[22] (19th century A.D.)

This book is written by *Lala Shaligrama Vaisya*. In *Ashtavarga Sarpagandha* is mentioned as *Nakuli* with synonyms like *Nakuli*, *Surasa*, *Nagsugandha*, *Gandhanakuli*, *Nakuleshta*, *Bhujakankshi*, *Sarpangi*, *Vishanashini* are described and as *Gandhanakuli* with synonyms like *Mahasugandha*, *Subaha*, *Gandhanakuli*, *Sarpakshi*, *Fadihantri*, *Nakuladhya*, *Ahibhuka*, *Vishamardanika*, *Ahimardini*, *Vishamardini*, *Mahahigandha*, *Ahilata* are described. Its properties are *Katu-Tikta- Kashay* in *Rasa*, *Ushna* in *Virya*, used in *Krimi Roga*, *Vrischika*, *Mooshika*, *Sarpadi Visha nashak*, *Tridosha-nashak*.

3.14 *Nighantu Adarsh*^[23] (1928 A.D.)

Written by *Vaidya Bapalala*, this book was published in two volumes. The basic principles of *Dravyaguna* are described in the first volume. *Sarpagandha* is described under *Kutajadi-Varga* with synonyms like *Dhawalvarua*, *Chandramarva*, *Sarpagandha*, *Chotachand* are described.

3.15 *Sankara Nighantu*^[24] (1935 A.D.)

The author of this *Nighantu* is *Rajavaidya Shankardutta Gauda*. He served as the *Adhyaksha* of *Jabalpur's Vanaushadhi Bhandara*. In 1935, this *Nighantu* was released. This book contains unique pharmaceutical formulas, various forms of *Putra*, *Yantra*, and medicinal herbs in detail, in addition to *Unani* medicines. *Sarpagandha* is found under first part as *Nakuli-Kand*, with the Names of it in *Sanskrit*, *Bengali*, *Marathi*, and *Farsi* have been given as *Nakuli*, *Gandhanakuli*, *Nakuli*, *Sugandha Nakuli*, *Mungusabela*, *Nai-Sapasand*, *Chotachand*, and mentioned as *Katu-Tikta* in *Rasa*, *Ushna* in *Virya*, *Tridosha-shamak*, indicated in different types of *Visha*, *Tridosha Shamak*.

3.16 *Mahausadha Nighantu*^[25] (1971 A.D.)

Shri L.P. Tripathi wrote the composition, *Aryadas Kumar Singh* put it together in 1971. Another well-known title for the book is "*Dravya Nama Guna Hastapustika*." It includes a thorough explanation of synonyms, *Guna*, *Karma*, *Habitat*, *Plant Morphology*. *Sarpagandha* is mentioned under *Mahausadhaadi varga* with synonyms like *Surasa*, *Sarpasugandha*, *Gandhanakuli*, *Nakuleshta*, *Bhujakankshi*, *Sarpabhuka*, *Vishanashini*, *Nakuli* are described. Its properties are *Katu-Tikta-Kashay* in *Rasa*, *Ushna* in *Virya*, is used in *Sarpa*, *Luta*, *Vrischik*, *Aakhu Visha*, *Visham-Jwara*, *Krimi Roga*, *Vrana Shamaka*, *Rakta-vata*.^[88]

3.17 *Ayurvediya Oshadhi Nighantu*^[26]

Written by *Kumaran Krishnan*, a renowned physician. It is the *Sanskrit* rendering of the Malayalam dictionary. In this book, several names of *Sarpagandha* have been mentioned in different places, like *Sarpagandha*, *Sarpakshi*, *Sarpadini*, *Sugandha*, *Nakuli*.

3.18 *Nighantu Siromani*^[27]

Written by *Raghava Kavi*, and a collection of *Sanskrit* names and medicinal properties of various medicinal plants from different *Nighantu*. In *Moolakadi-varga* *Sarpagandha* is described as *Nakuli- Nakulkanda* with synonyms like *Nakuli*, *Naag-gandha*, *Ahibhuka*, *Surasa*, *Sarpadini*, *Vyaalgandha*, *Sarpasugandha*, *Bhogigandhika*, *Rochakapatrika*, *Nakuleshta*, *Mahateertha*, *Vishaghi*, *Subaha*, *Sunanda*, *Vishadranshti*, *Chirpatrika*, *Nagsugandha*, *Bhujangakshi*, *Sarpangi*, *Vishanasha*, are described.

3.19 *Abhidanmanjari*^[28]

In *Prarambh Shloka* of this book, written by *Bhishagacharya*. In this book, *Sarpagandha* is described under *sankeerna-varga* as *Sarpagandha* with synonyms like *Yogeshwari*, *Nakuli*,

Ishwari, Bheeritapatrika, Sarpagandha, Bhogigandhika, Vishaghni are mentioned. as other *Sarpagandha* with synonyms like *Sarpasugandha, Nakulpriya, Nakuleshta, Sarpakshi, Chatraki, Vishamardini* are described.

3.20 *Priya Nighantu* (1983 century A.D.)^[29]

Priya Vrat Sharma wrote this *Nighantu* in the 20th century A.D. In honor of himself, he has given this book the name *Priya Nighantu*. Synonyms of *Sarpagandha*, such as *Chandrika, Dhawalvitapa*, are mentioned. Its properties are *Ati-tikta Rasa, Ushna Virya Nidrajanana*. used in *Shoola, Jwara, Unmada, Krimi roga, Rakta-vata*.

3.21 *Ayurvedokta Oushadha Niruktamala*^[30]

This *Kosha* has been written by *Vaidya J.L.N. Sastry*. It is based on etymological derivations of Single drugs. Synonyms and names of Medicinal plants are given in it. Synonyms of *Sarpagandha* as *Ahilata, Gandhanakuli, Chandramara, Vishamardini, Sarpagandha*.

4 Classification of *Sarpagandha* in different *Nighantus*

<i>Nighantu</i>	<i>Varga</i>	References
<i>Paryayatnamala</i>	-----	235, Pg. 82
<i>Candra or Madanadi Nighantu</i>	<i>Prakareeran Aushadhiya Dravya</i>	146,147 Pg.217
<i>Dhanvantari Nighantu</i>	<i>Karveeradi varga</i>	91,92 Pg.137
<i>Nighantu shesa</i>	<i>Gulma Kanda</i>	Pg. 220
<i>Sodhala Nighantu</i>	<i>Guduchyadi varga & Karveeradi varga</i>	186 537
<i>Abhidhanaratnamala</i>	<i>Katu Dravya Skanda</i>	19
<i>Hridayadipaka Nighantu</i>	<i>Chatushpada varga</i>	17
<i>Madanpala Nighantu</i>	<i>Abhayadi varga</i>	263
<i>Raj Nighantu</i>	<i>Moolakadi varga</i>	93
<i>Kaiyadeva Nighantu</i>	<i>Oshadhi varga</i>	775-777
<i>Bhavaprakasa Nighantu</i>	<i>Haritakyadi varga</i>	165-166
<i>Paryayamuktavali</i>	<i>Tambulyaadi-Lata varga</i>	11, Pg.118
<i>Shaligram Nighantu</i>	<i>Ashtadi varga</i>	Pg.142
<i>Nighantu Adarsha</i>	<i>Kutajadi varga</i>	Pg.864-866
<i>Shankara Nighantu</i>	<i>Nakuli kanda</i>	Pg. 152
<i>Mahausadha Nighantu</i>	<i>Mahausadhadi varga</i>	17-18, Pg 41
<i>Ayurvediya Oshadhi Nighantu</i>	-----	Pg 372, 754, 755, 775
<i>Nighantu Siromani</i>	<i>Moolakadi varga</i>	52-55, Pg. 126
<i>Abhidhan Manjari</i>	<i>Sankeerna varga</i>	1111, Pg.183
<i>Priya Nighantu</i>	<i>Shatpuspadi varga</i>	163-164, Pg.106
<i>Ayurvedokta Oushadha Niruktamala</i>

5 *Sarpagandha* in *Kosha Grantha*

5.1 *Vacaspatyam*^[31]

Vacaspatyam (*Brihat samskratabhidhanam*) is written by *Shri Taranatha Tarkavacaspati Bhattacharya*. Synonyms of *Sarpagandha*, along with their interpretation, are mentioned at various places. *Gandhanakuli* (vol. 4. pg. 2524), *Nakuleshta* (vol. 5. pg. 3926), *Nakuli* (vol. 5. Pg 4008), *Naggandha* (vol. 5. pg. 4011), *Nag Sugandha* (vol. 5. pg. 4017), *Sarpagandha* (vol. 6. pg. 5257), *Sarpangi* (vol. 6. pg 5257), synonyms are described.

5.2 *Dravyaguna kosha*^[32] (1997 A.D.)

Dravyaguna Kosha, written by *Priya Vrata Sharma*, was published in 1997. The *Kosha* contains different synonyms of plants and their meanings. Synonyms of *Sarpagandha* have been mentioned as *Sarpagandha*, *Sarpakankalika*, *Sarpagandhakhya*, *Sarpachatrika*, *Sarpasugandha* on page 189.

5.3 *Sabdakalpadruma*^[33] (20th Century A.D.)

This *Kosha* by *Shree Raja Radhakanta Deva Bahadura* contains synonyms of *Sarpagandha* as *Gandhanakuli* (vol. 2 pg 302), *Gandhamoola* (vol. 2 pg 303), *Nakuli* (vol. 2. Pg. 846), *Nakuleshta* (vol. 2. Pg. 813), *Nakulakhya* (vol. 2. Pg. 813), *Naggandha* (vol. 2 pg. 848), *Nagsugandha* (vol. 2. pg. 851), *Maha sugandha* (vol. 3 pg. 676), *Mahavirya* (vol. 3. Pg. 674), *Vishaghni* (vol. 4. pg. 445), *Vishanashini* (vol. 4. pg. 445), *Sarpagandha* (vol. 5 pg. 301), *Sarpakankalika* (vol. 5. Pg 301), *Sarpadini* (vol 5. Pg. 302), *Sarpakshi* (vol.5 pg. 302).

5.4 *Bedi-Vanaspati Kosha*^[34] (1997 A.D.)

This *Kosha* has been written by Prof. *Ramesh Bedi*. It has been published in 6 volumes. With the intention of providing information on all plants that can be used medicinally. Synonyms and names of *Sarpagandha* as *Bada Chandrika* (vol. 4, pg 313), *Sarpakankalika* (vol. 6, pg 44), *Sarpagandha* (vol. 6, pg. 45), *Sarpagandhini* (vol. 6, pg. 45), *Sarpalochana* (vol. 6, pg. 47), *Sarpasugandhika* (vol. 6, pg. 47), and *Sarpangi* (vol. 6, pg. 48), *Sarpadini* (vol. 6, Pg 48).

6 Sanskrit synonyms of *Sarpagandha* are described in various *Nighantus*

Numerous synonyms of *Sarpagandha* have been mentioned in various *Nighantus* like, *Nakuli*, *Surasa*, *Nagsugandha*, *Gandhanakuli*, *Nakuleshta*, *Bhujangakshi*, *Sarpangi*, *Vishanashini*, *Sarpagandha*, *Sugandha*, *Raktapatrika*, *Ishwari*, *Naggandha*, *Ahibhuka*, *Swarasa*, *Sarpadini*, *Vyaalgandha*, *Bhogigandhika*, *Sarpasugandha*, *Ciritaptraka*,

Mahavirya, Sarpasugandhika, Vishaghni, Subaha, Sarpalochana, Sarpakankalika, Sunanda, Vishadranshtika, Gandhamoola, Surabhi, Gandhakhya, Gandhacharini, Samaha, Sarpagandhini, Mahasarpanetra, Rochakapatrika, Dhawalvarua, Chotachand, Nakulkand, Dhanvarua, Gandharasna, Harkai-chandra, Badachandrika, Sarpagandhakhya, Sarpachatrika, Yogeshwari, Bheeritapatrika, Bhoga-gandhika, Sarpabhuka, Fadihantri, Nakuladhya, Ahibhuka, Vishamardanika, Ahimardini, Vishamardini, Mahahigandha, Ahilata, Rishyagandha, Sarpagandha, Rishijangalika, Nakulya, Atigandhika.

Table 1.0: Sanskrit synonyms of Sarpagandha described in different nighantus.

Sr. No.	Sanskrit Name	Nighantus																			
		1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	20
1.	Atigandhika		+																		
2.	Ahibhuka								+					+					+		
3.	Ahimardini													+							
4.	Ahilata													+							
5.	Bheeritapatrika																				+
6.	Bhogigandhika			+															+	+	
7.	Bhujakankshi											+					+		+		
8.	Chandrika																				+
9.	Chandramarva														+						
10.	Chatraki										+										+
11.	Chirpatrika																		+		
12.	Ciritaptraka		+	+	+						+										
13.	Chirnapatrika					+															
14.	Chotachand								+					+	+						
15.	Dhawalvarua								+					+							
16.	Dhawalvitapa																				+
17.	Dhanvarua								+												
18.	Fadihantri													+							
19.	Gandhamoola					+															
20.	Gandhanakuli							+	+		+	+		+		+	+				
21.	Gandharasna																				
22.	Gandhakhya					+															
23.	Gandhacharini					+															
24.	Harkai chandra								+												
25.	Ishwari					+				+											+
26.	Kamacharini										+										
27.	Kshiri						+														
28.	Mahasugandha														+						
29.	Mahasudha										+										
30.	Mahavirya										+										
31.	Mahahigandha														+						
32.	Mahateertha																			+	

16. Mahausadha Nighantu 17. Ayurvediya Oshadhi Nighantu 18. Nighantu Shiromani 19. Abhidhanmanjari 20. Priya Nighantu

7. Etymology of Sanskrit Synonyms of Sarpagandha.

Sr.	Sanskrit synonym	Etymology	Reference
1.	<i>Nakuli</i>	(नकुलेन दृष्टा पीता वाः) Grows in mountain or hilly areas.	<i>Sa.k.d.</i> : pg. 846 vol. 2
2.	<i>Surasa</i>	शोभनो रसो यस्याः Has exudation or latex.	<i>Sa.k.d.</i> : pg. 382 vol. 5
3.	<i>Nagsugandha</i>	(नागस्येव सु शोभनो गन्धो यस्याः) Grows in hilly areas having a peculiar smell.	<i>Sa.k.d.</i> : pg. 851 vol. 2
4.	<i>Sarpakankalika</i>	सर्पस्य कङ्गालमिवाङ्ग यस्याः Roots look like Sarpa.	<i>Sa.k.d.</i> : pg. 301 vol. 5
5.	<i>Sarpakshi</i>	सर्पस्य अक्षीव पुष्पं यस्याः Fruits when ripe looks like the eye of the snake.	<i>Sa.k.d.</i> : pg. 302 vol. 5
6.	<i>Sarpadini</i>	सर्पस्य तद्विषस्य अदनं भक्षणं यस्यः	<i>Sa.k.d.</i> : pg. 302 vol. 5
7.	<i>Vishadranshtika</i>	विषं दंष्ट्रायर्था यस्याः visaghna property.	<i>Sa.k.d.</i> : pg. 445 vol. 4
8.	<i>Vishanashini</i>	विषं नाशयतीति : antitoxic.	<i>Sa.k.d.</i> : pg. 445 vol. 4
9.	<i>Sumahakanda</i>	Roots have an agreeable smell.	
10.	<i>Raktapushpika</i>	Flowers are red in colour.	
11.	<i>Sarpagandha</i>	सर्प गन्धयते हिनस्तीति: Roots have a typical smell like that of Sarpa, and this smell drives away the Sarpa.	<i>Sa.k.d.</i> : pg. 301 vol. 5
12.	<i>Naggandha</i>	नागस्य गन्ध इव गन्धो यस्याः Taken as Nakuli, and has antitoxic action.	<i>Sa.k.d.</i> : pg. 848 vol. 2
13.	<i>Sugandha</i>	शोभनो गन्धो यस्याः	<i>Sa.k.d.</i> : pg. 365 vol. 5
14.	<i>Nakuleshta</i>	नकुलानामिष्टा प्रियाः Commonly found on hilly regions.	<i>Sa.k.d.</i> : pg. 813 vol. 2
15.	<i>Mahavirya</i>	महत् वीर्यमस्याः A potent drug.	<i>Sa.k.d.</i> : pg. 674 vol. 3
16.	<i>Dhawalvitapa</i>	Purifies the body.	
17.	<i>Maha sugandha</i>	महान् सुगन्धोऽस्याः	<i>Sa.k.d.</i> : pg. 676 vol. 3

8. Properties and Actions of *Sarpagandha* according to *Nighantus*

Different *Nighantus* have mentioned different properties of *Sarpagandha*. Most of them have said *Sarpagandha* to be *Katu* and *Tikta* in *Rasa*, *Ruksha* in *Guna*, *Sheeta* in *Virya*. They have said *Sarpagandha* to be *kaphavatahara* in action. They have mentioned *Unmada*, *Apasmara*, *Agnimandya*, *Mastishkavikara*, *Anidra*, *Krimiroga*, *Amajavibandhashoola*, *Raktabharadhikya*, *Sarpavisha*, where *Sarpagandha* is used extensively.

Table 1.1: Properties and actions of *Sarpagandha* described in various *Nighantus*.

Sr. no.	<i>Nighantu</i>	<i>Rasa</i>	<i>Guna</i>	<i>Virya</i>	<i>Vipaka</i>	<i>Doshkarma</i>	<i>Other karma</i>	<i>Roghanata</i>	<i>Ref.</i>
1.	<i>Paryayaratn amala</i>								<i>Paryaya: Shloka 235</i>
2.	<i>Candra Nighantu</i>	<i>Tikta Rasa Kashaya Anurasa</i>		<i>Sheeta</i>		<i>Tridoshashama ka</i>	<i>Rasayana, Medhya, Kushtha, Apasmara</i>	<i>Bhedana, Luta-Vrana-Nivarak</i>	<i>Prakareeran Aushadhiya Dravya 146,147 Pg.217</i>
3.	<i>Madanadi Nighantu</i>	<i>Tikta Kashaya</i>	-	<i>Ushna</i>	-	-	<i>Bhedana</i>	<i>Sarpa, Luta, Vrischika, Mooshika Visha Nashak</i>	<i>Prakareenya Aushadhiya dravya Uttar Bhag Shloka 146-147</i>
4.	<i>Dhanvantri Nighantu</i>	<i>Katu-Tikta</i>	-	<i>Ushna</i>	-	-	-	<i>Mooshika Visha, Krimi Nashak</i>	<i>Karveeradi varga shloka 91-92</i>
5.	<i>Nighantu Shesha</i>	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	<i>Gulma Kanda Shloka 220</i>
6.	<i>Sodhala Nighantu</i>	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	<i>Guduchyadi Varga Shloka 186 Karveeradi Varga Shloka 537</i>
7.	<i>Abhidhanar amamala</i>	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	<i>Katu-dravya Skanda Shloka19</i>
8.	<i>Hridyadipaka Nighantu</i>								<i>Chatushpada Varga Shloka 17</i>
9.	<i>Madanapala Nighantu</i>	<i>Tikta</i>	<i>Ruksha</i>	<i>Ushna</i>	<i>Katu</i>	<i>Kapha-vata Nashak</i>	-	<i>Vrana, Krimi, Sarpa, Luta, Vrischika, Aakhu, Mooshika, Visha Nashak</i>	<i>Abhayadi varga shloka 263-264</i>
10.	<i>Raja</i>	<i>Tikta-</i>	-	<i>Ushna</i>	-	<i>Tridoshashama</i>	-	<i>Visha Nashak</i>	<i>Moolakadi</i>

	Nighantu	Katu				ka			Varga Shloka 93
11.	Kaiyadeva Nighantu	Katu-Tikta-Kashaya	-	-	-	-		Vrana, Krimi, Sarpa, Luta, Vrishchika, Mooshika Visha, and Gara Visha Nashak	Oshadhi varga Shloka 775-777
12.	Bhavprakasa Nighantu	Kashaya, Tikta, Katu	-	Ushna	-	-	-	Vrana, Krimi, Jwara Shamak, Sarpa, Luta, Vrishchika, Aakhu, Mooshika Visha Nashak	Haritakyadi varga shloka 165-166
13.	Paryayamuktavali	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	Tambulyaadi-Latavarga Shloka 11
14.	Saligram Nighantu	Kashaya, Tikta, Katu	-	Ushna	-	Tridoshashamaka		Krimi, Vrana Nashak, Sarpa, Luta, Vrishchika, Mooshika Visha Nashak	Ashtadi varga
15.	Nighantu Adarsh	-	-	-	-	-	Nidraprada,	Unmada, Apasmara, Raktachaapshamak	Kutajadi varga
16.	Shankara Nighantu	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	Nakuli kanda
17.	Mahausadhana Nighantu	Kashaya, Tikta, Katu	-	Ushna	-	-	-	Vrana, Krimi Shamak, Visham Jwara Shamak, Rakta-vata Sarpa, Luta, Vrishchika, Aakhu, Mooshika Visha Nashak	Mahausadhadi varga:17-18
18.	Ayurvediya Oshadhi Nighantu	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	Ayu. Os. Ni.
19.	Nighantu Siromani	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	Moolakadi varga:52-55
20.	Abhidhanmanjari	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	Sankeerna varga:1111
21.	Priya Nighantu	Ati-tikta	-	Ushna	-	-	Nidrajanana	Shoola, Jwara, Unmada, Krimi roga, and Rakta-vata	Shatpuspadi varga:163-164

9. Uses of Sarpagandha as an ingredient in different important Ayurvedic formulations.

Sr.	Formulation	Indication	Reference.
1.	Lasunadi varga siddha Ghrith	Grahadosha, Manas Vikara.	Su. Ut. 60/48
2.	Eksar Yoga	Sarpavisha	Su.Ka.5/84

3.	<i>Makoyadi Ghrit</i>	<i>Arunaadi-Panch-Sarpa-Dansta</i>	<i>Su.Ka.7/29</i>
4.	<i>Hinguadi Yoga</i>	<i>Grahabhootnashak</i>	<i>Ah. Ut.5/3</i>
5.	<i>Kshara-Agada</i>	<i>Vata Gulma, Manas Vikara.</i>	<i>Bhe.Ci.5/40</i>
6.	<i>Jatyaadikam Taila</i>	<i>Sannipatika Jwara and Tridoshaj Roga</i>	<i>Vai. Pr. 4.</i>
7.	<i>Bhootpratishede Vasti</i>	<i>Graha, Unmada, Apasmara Roga</i>	<i>Vai. Pr. 8.</i>
8.	<i>Dhadhi-taila-ghritair-alodhya-deya</i>	<i>Sheeta Jwara and Siro-Ruja</i>	<i>Vai. Pr. 10.</i>
9.	<i>Paisachika-ghrita</i>	<i>Unmada, Apasmara Roga</i>	<i>Yog. Rt. Sa. pg.51</i>
10.	<i>Palankashadhya Taila</i>	<i>Apasmara Roga</i>	<i>Cakra.21/31-33</i>
11.	<i>Mahapaisachik Ghrit</i>	<i>Chaturthak Jwara, Grahadosha, Unmada, and Apasmara Roga</i>	<i>Ga.ni.pr.kh. 1/363</i>
12.	<i>Aparajita-Agad.</i>	<i>Bhootounmada</i>	<i>Ga.ni.rog.kh. 1/55</i>
13.	<i>Kadambadi Taila</i>	<i>Kaksha, Vidhradhi, Visarpa Roga</i>	<i>Vai. Mano. 11/13</i>
14.	<i>Vartigrahadi Lepa</i>	<i>Vrana Shaman</i>	<i>Vai. Mano. 16/99</i>

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

After analysing various text we found a very important role of *Sarpagandha* in *manas roga*. because most of the *Sarpagandha* formulations were found in treatment of these diseases. *Sarpagandha* was said to be as *Prashast Aushad* or *Param Aushad* for all types of *Visha* in many *samhitas*. After review of *Sarpagandha* in various *Nighantus* only synonyms of *Sarpagandha* were found while in some *nighantus* synonyms and its properties like *rasa panchaka* and *karma* has been mentioned. *Sarpagandha* was not mentioned in many texts such as *Vedic Nighantu*, *Sausruta Nighantu*, *Siddhasara Nighantu*, *Harmekhala Nighantu*, *Ashtanga Nighantu*, *Camatkara Nighantu*, *Dravyaguna Sangraha*, *Sabdacandrika*, *Madhava Dravyaguna*, *Siddhamantra and Prakasha*, *Ayurveda Mahodadhi*, *Gunaratnamala*, *Saraswati Nighantu*, *Raj Vallabha Nighantu*, *Laghu Nighantu*. While in *Abhidanmanjari*, *Saraswati Nighantu*, *Paryaymuktavali* and *Shaligram Nighantu* only synonyms of *Sarpagandha* have been mentioned but *guna karma* has been not mentioned.

Chandra Nighantu, has mentioned that *Sarpagandha* has *Sheeta Virya* contrary to what most of the *Nighantus* state as *Sarpagandha* being *Ushna* in *Virya*. In most of the *Nighantu* *Sarpagandha* is said to have *Kashaya* and *Tikta Rasa* but in *Priya Nighantu*, it is said to be *Ati-tikta*. *Sarpagandha* is said to have *Katu Tikta*, *Kashaya Rasa* in *Kaiyadeva Nighantu* and *Bhavprakash Nighantu*, *Sarpagandha* is said to be *Bhedana* and in *Chandra Nighantu*, and *Jwara shamak* in *Priya Nighantu* and *Bhavaprakasa Nighantu*.

CONCLUSION

The extensive review of *Sarpagandha* in various *Ayurvedic* treatise like *Samhitas*, *Nighantu*, *Kosha Grantha* and *Rasa Grantha* concluded to the fact that *Sarpagandha* has a wide range of therapeutic qualities as it is seen in the treatment of numerous diseases in the form of an ingredient. *Sarpagandha* has been mentioned in ancient *Samhitas* and *Nighantu* indicates its established use since many years. Also, the large number of synonyms of *Sarpagandha* indicates that it has been a popular medicinal plant with uses indicated in its name itself like *Nakuli*, *Gandhanakuli*, *Nakuleshta*, *Vishanashini*, *Sarpagandha*, etc. This extensive review of the plant *Sarpagandha* will bring to light its underrated importance and help the *Ayurvedic* practioners in various ailments. It will also make it easy for the *Ayurvedic* scholars to conduct further research studies on *Sarpagandha*.

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